

Test entries were planted in two rows of 10 hills each, alternated with a skip row of susceptible check TN1. Closer spacing (15 × 10 cm) and a topdressing of extra N above the recommended dose were used to induce higher BPH incidence in the trials. We scored entries in the field during peak BPH incidence and when TN1 died.

Promising entries that recorded BPH damage score of 2-3 were BPT2217, BPT4363, BPT4365, RP2332-19-9-6, RP2362-227-22, RP2542-1657-194, RP2543-1444-46, RP2543-1464-152, local check ADT36, and local resistant check PY3 (see table). RP1746-1723-8, RP2332-16-3, and RP2332-18-15 were resistant to BPH (score 3), but susceptible to leafhopper. □

Sources of resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) in rice

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We studied 108 rice cultivars to identify sources of resistance to the local biotype of BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) under laboratory conditions using the bulk seedling test.

Test entries were sown in 20-cm rows, 5 cm apart, in 60- × 45- × 10-cm wooden boxes at Rice Research Station, Moncompu, Kerala, from 1985 to 1988. Each box contained 24 lines including four of susceptible check TN1 and two of resistant check PTB33.

Seedlings were thinned to 20 per row at 7 d. Seedboxes were placed inside 70- × 55- × 15-cm trays with 5 cm of water in them. Trays were kept inside a screening cage. After 1 wk each seedling was infested with an average of five second-instar BPH nymphs. Damage was scored by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) scale when about 90% of TN1 had died. Screening was repeated three times.

Forty rice cultivars were resistant (see table), 22 moderately resistant, 13 moderately susceptible, and 33 highly susceptible. Resistant entries were of diverse origin: Indonesia (1), Sri Lanka (3), Philippines (7), and India (29). Of the Indian types, 13 (and PTB33) were from Kerala. □

Resistant entries and BPH score.^a

Designation	Origin	Damage score (0-9)	Designation	Origin	Damage score (0-9)
Sinna Sivappu	Sri Lanka	2.9	RP1015-45-114-1	India	1.8
Lekham Samba	Sri Lanka	2.6	KAU1734-2 ^b	India	2.9
Kuru Hondarawala	Sri Lanka	1.2	RP1015-100-25-4	India	2.7
IR40	Philippines	2.4	KAU2084 ^b	India	1.2
IR25984-92-1-3	Philippines	2.5	KAU169 ^b	India	2.7
IR1552	Philippines	1.2	KAU126 ^b	India	2.6
IR5741-73-2-3	Philippines	2.8	KAU153-1 ^b	India	1.6
IR22082-41-2	Philippines	2.1	KAU168 ^b	India	2.7
IR24	Philippines	2.5	KAU93 ^b	India	2.2
IR9830-26-3-3	Philippines	2.7	MO 4 ^b	India	2.8
CR266-407-4	India	1.2	MO 5 ^b	India	2.6
RP2695-5-7-32	India	1.5	MO 6 ^b	India	2.0
RP2068-32-2-2	India	1.6	MO 7 ^b	India	2.0
MTU5194	India	1.7	M102 ^b	India	2.9
RP2695-5-8-31	India	1.9	RP1015-15-7-7-2	India	2.9
MTU5295	India	1.7	RP1579-73-1864	India	2.8
RP2068-17-2-2	India	1.6	RP1579-1863-73-32-53	India	2.8
RP1579-56-1907	India	1.6	ARC6650	India	2.9
RP1756-39	India	1.4	M66-B-45-1	Indonesia	1.8
TNAU BPHR8275	India	2.4	PTB33 (resistant check) ^b	India	2.4
MTU4870	India	1.6	TN1 (susceptible check)	Taiwan	8.7

^aScored by SES. All entries except TN1 were resistant. ^bFrom Kerala.

Virulence of a new biotype of brown planthopper (BPH) in Mekong Delta

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Six BPH populations from five ecological areas in the Mekong Delta were collected to determine their virulence on rice using the modified bulk seedling test.

Differential check varieties were seeded in 20-cm rows, 5 cm apart, in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes with three replications. Test varieties were infested 7 d after seeding with 5-8 second- and third-instar nymphs per seedling. Damage was visually rated using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1-9) when the susceptible check TN1 had died.

All new biotype populations killed TN1. Mudgo (*Bph 1*) was moderately

Reaction^a of BPH on differential check varieties, Mekong Delta, 1990-91.

Site, season	Host of BPH population	BPH score ^a on					
		TN1 (none)	Mudgo (<i>Bph 1</i>)	ASD7 (<i>bph 2</i>)	Rathu Heenati (<i>Bph 3</i>)	PTB33 (digenic)	Babawee (<i>bph 4</i>)
Angiang	IR64	9	7	9	3	3	3
1990 WS		9	7	7	3	0	3
1991 DS	MTL 85	9	7	7	0	1	5
Angiang		9	5	9	5	0	3
1990 WS	MTL 85	9	5	7	5	0	5
1991 DS		9	5	9	5	0	5
Tiengiang	OM59-7	9	5	7	3	1	1
1990 WS		9	5	9	3	1	5
1991 DS	IR42	9	3	7	1	0	7
Haugiang		9	3	7	1	0	7
1990 WS	IR19660	9	7	9	5	0	5
1991 DS		9	7	9	5	0	5

^aAv of 3 replications. By the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale.